

METHODOLOGY FOR THE INTEGRATION OF DATA-BASED MODELS IN PRODUCTION ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract: *Many of the key digitization projects in companies involve data modeling. There are numerous methodologies that describe what to do in the different stages of data modeling projects, but these do not describe how to do it or what architectures or technologies to use for the correct performance of the same. In practice, a multitude of technologies and heterogeneous tools coexist and are used ad hoc according to the needs of each model. In most cases, the processes of training, validation, deployment, monitoring and retraining of the models are carried out without a common technology framework that serves as a reference for all the projects belonging to the same field, which makes the management of the models and their life cycle very difficult. This paper presents a proposal for a methodology and architecture based on virtualization technologies, which will serve as a guide for the correct execution of data modelling projects and which will make it possible to manage the phases of data analysis, model development, implementation in production, testing of new configurations and monitoring.*

Keywords: Project Management, Systems architecture, Data Modeling Methodologies

1. Introduction

Nowadays, intelligent systems give solutions to a multitude of problems that until a few years ago people were unable to solve. For the correct development and exploitation of these systems, knowledge is needed in different areas such as artificial intelligence, which is in charge of the study and design of algorithms capable of making intelligent decisions, data science whose objective is the treatment, analysis and modelling of problems, and data engineering, capable of designing architectures and implementing systems able of executing these models efficiently and satisfying user demand. With the aim of guiding and helping experts from different areas of knowledge to cooperate and solve the problems they face when developing data modeling projects, the need arises to develop and apply methodologies that define which tasks must be carried out at each stage of the project life cycle for their correct execution.

There are numerous methodologies that describe what to do in the different stages of data modeling projects, but these do not describe how to do it or what architectures or technologies to use for the correct performance of the same. On the other hand, there is no common technology framework that serves as a reference for all projects in this area, but rather there are many heterogeneous tools and systems.

The growing importance of data-based models is dramatically transforming the way we work. Until recently, it was most common to train models off-line (without processing live data from users or ensuring that the service they provide remains available during such training), and then put the model into production. However, the number of models is increasing and with more demanding monitoring requirements, so methodologies and technologies are needed to enable this:

- Minimize the time to put into production in order to speed up the future deployment of a greater number of models.
- Define monitoring metrics for supervised learning type models. Supervised models are those in which a set of observations defined by variables or characteristics is provided in the training phase, in addition to the expected output(s) for each of these instances of the input data set.
- To be able to visualize the quality of the predictions that the models are sending to the user and if these begin to degrade, retrain the models with new data.
- Avoid problems of library compatibility and dependencies between models.

To achieve this transformation, well-known international companies are developing their own platforms. One of the best-known cases is Uber's platform, called Michelangelo [1], although models of companies such as Amazon, Netflix, Twitter or Paypal are also outstanding. Attempts to streamline the process are not only focused on the technological part, but also on establishing a defined workflow. Thus, for example, the work of Zaharia et al. [2] describes the workflow and life cycle followed by Machine Learning projects in an organization, called MLFlow. Similarly, Hummer et al [3] describe a DevOps-based life cycle, called in this case ModelOps.

The present work includes a proposal of methodology and architecture that serves as a guide for the correct execution of data modeling projects, specifically about models on Machine Learning; subfield of artificial intelligence in charge of the elaboration of models capable of generalizing behaviors from an input information.

This communication proposes an architecture for the management of the phases of data analysis, development of Machine Learning models, implementation in production, testing of new configurations and monitoring of these. The architecture is especially designed for companies where, due to the confidentiality requirements of the data they handle, cloud-based solutions are not acceptable, but rather "on premise" solutions are required (software solutions whose installation is carried out within the company's own servers and ICT infrastructure).

2. Analysis of existing platforms for Machine Learning

As a starting point, the possibility of adopting one of the many existing platforms is considered. The Gartner report about leading platforms in the market [4] shows that the three largest companies with platforms for Data Science and Machine Learning have not been able to enter or remain in the segment of leaders, which shows the great evolution that exists in this segment. Most relevant existing commercial platforms are analysed.

- Machine Learning Server [5]: Microsoft platform allows local deployment with different configurations to build an automatic learning platform, in addition to supporting the R and Python programming languages. However, as it is not an Open-source technology, license is needed. It requires SQL Server which limits the freedom of choice of the database. Finally, the platform does not implement any control of the performance of the models in production, nor a way to retrain and update them when their accuracy begins to degrade.
- H2O [6]: The platform facilitates the process of putting into production the Machine Learning models that they provide. However, the platform is oriented to the processing of Big Data, since the supported databases are oriented to large amounts of data. On the other hand, when serialising the models in Java objects, difficulties may arise when it comes to importing these into the users' current .NET applications.
- Azure Databricks [7]: Provides a working environment for collaboration between the different roles involved in a data modeling project, in addition to cloud processing and access to multiple Apache tools, such as Spark. The problem with this technology is that it does not allow local deployment, only in the Azure Cloud in addition of being a fully paid tool despite using numerous Spark Open-source tools.
- Azure Machine Learning [8]: A cloud-based platform that facilitates the effort of developing data models and performing analysis through an interface that acts as an interactive canvas.

It is more focused on users who are unfamiliar with programming languages than on advanced users of R and Python. In contrast, it has the disadvantages of not allowing local deployment, nor does it offer metrics for monitoring models in production.

- DeployR [9]: It only allows support for working with models developed in R. It is a technology that had its boom in the past when it was Open-source, currently because it is a paid tool, it must be licensed with Machine Learning Server and it does not provide novelties with respect to other Open-Source technologies that offer similar characteristics; it has fallen into disuse.
- OpenCPU [10]: It allows the local production of models developed in R. It facilitates the creation of API's and the distributed data processing, releasing the computing load of the user's equipment. But it does not support Python nor does it offer performance metrics or model update options.
- SAS Decision Manager [11]: It is a tool that facilitates the construction of workflow throughout the life cycle of a data modeling project. It is also the only tool that provides performance metrics and model updating mechanisms for systems in production. However, it does not offer any compatibility with Python and R languages, as the management of each stage must be customized through the SAS programming language. This leads to extra training for all team members who are going to use SAS and the abandonment of the languages they worked with until now. It is a very expensive tool in terms of training, as well as acquisition.
- Google Cloud Machine Learning [12]: Cloud service that covers the training and production phases of certain Machine Learning models offered by the scikit-learn library or the XGBoost algorithm, in addition to providing support for all Deep Learning models developed with the TensorFlow library. It does not allow local deployment, nor support for custom models that the user develops in languages such as R and Python. In addition, to cover certain phases of the development life cycle it is necessary to use other Google Cloud services. It also does not offer performance metrics or model update mechanisms. In short, Google Cloud Machine Learning is service oriented more towards providing computing capacity for Deep Learning models than to serving as a support platform for all types of Machine Learning algorithms.
- Amazon SageMaker [13]: this platform aims to facilitate the data access, training and production workflow of data models. It also offers predefined algorithms to simplify modeling for users without programming knowledge. However, this platform does not allow local deployment.

From the analysis, it is concluded that there is no commercial platform that fully satisfies the needs set out for the application case, so an own architecture is proposed that allows the definition of a unique workflow for the data modeling projects, as well as the necessary technologies so that each of the steps implicit in the project life cycle can be carried out.

3. Description of the proposed architecture

The architecture is intended to support the following workflow steps: data collection, data preparation, training and monitoring. The architecture finally proposed is oriented to microservices. This design allows the decomposition of the different functionalities involved in the execution of a data modelling project into small services whose communication is carried out through light mechanisms. These services will be managed and encapsulated through containers. Figure 1 contains each of the components of the system. Technologies are grouped according to the four steps of the workflow. In addition, it is delimited when the work is done offline and online. The online line marks the separation between development and production microservices (the latter being the ones located at the top of the line).

Figure 1 Architecture of product deployment

Datalake will be managed with MySQL, although the data source in a general environment could be very diverse. One of the services that the architecture incorporates is to allow model developers to remotely execute the model analysis and training process. The training phase can require a lot of time and a great deal of computing capacity that developers do not have in their local teams. For this reason, two technologies are proposed that allow remote execution of code in the R and Python languages on dedicated servers. There are two variants for data preparation, one for R and one for Python. Figures 2 and 3 describe each of the processes. In the case of R, data processing is done with the RStudio Server tool [14], while in the case of Python, the Pycharm IDE [15] is used.

- RStudio Server is the Open-source platform that provides a web interface to an R version running on a remote Linux server. The IDE is similar to RStudio which would make it easier for the user to adapt to the work environment since it is currently the IDE that the development team is using; it incorporates the tools for displaying graphics, history, debugging, and managing the workspace. The deployment of RStudio Server will be done from a predefined base image containing the specific libraries and dependencies that the team considers appropriate, so that each development of the different R models will be based on the same libraries with the same version number. Once the image is executed the container is created, the data engineers will be able to have remote access to its working directory and greater computing capacity.
- Pycharm is a development IDE for Python. Unlike RStudio Server, which provided a remote server to run, store, and manage R files, Pycharm only provides remote code execution, via ssh connection to the server or using containers. The user must manage his scripts locally. When executing remote code Pycharm provides the option to deploy a container, execute the code remotely and return the result to the user when the container finishes its execution. For each execution a new container is created which mounts the Pycharm project directory to the container for execution; the container is then removed. All dependencies and libraries must be installed in the container to be used as a remote interpreter.

The output in both cases is a historical data set managed by Cassandra [16]. Cassandra is the platform used in this architecture to store historical data, new data obtained from user applications and predictions made by the models. Due to the diversity of data that may be received in the future, a NoSQL database has been chosen to store unstructured data. Cassandra is the leading NoSQL distributed database management system and is column-oriented, designed to manage large amounts of data. The data structures used in Cassandra are more specific than those used in

relational databases, allowing for faster read and write speeds; a typical use for Cassandra is in web applications that work with real-time requests.

Figure 2 Data preparation with R

Figure 3 Data preparation with Python

The training process also takes place within the development microservices. Once each model has been developed, along with each version produced for validation, the corresponding production services are developed. These can be deployed as single instances or using Docker Swarm technology (technology to deploy containers in multiple nodes) in case high availability is required. Once in production, these would return the predictions to the users' applications and

store the "Live Data" in the database instance dedicated to host such information. All this information is made accessible to the user through a monitoring dashboard.

The design of the proposed monitoring dashboard developed in Python on Dash framework [17] is shown in Figure 4. The content of each field is dynamically updated based on the data modifications in Cassandra and the user actions in the application; these types of components are called reactive components. This framework allows the creation of reactive components with callbacks in the functions that are part of the application's controller. The reactive components of the application are as follows:

- Model selector: Allows you to select the model in production that you want to display in the web application.
- Retraining: Retrains the selected model with all the data available in Cassandra, that is, historical data is added along with the live data. Since several versions may exist for each model, the version selected by the user will be taken into account.
- Version selection: Allows to visualize the graphic evolution and the numerical metrics of the different trained versions of the same model.
- To Champion: Button that allows to convert a challenger or champion candidate version, which means that the answers to the users' requests will be made by the version of the new model selected.
- Current list of champion and challenger models.
- Variable selector: Selecting a model and its version, allows to choose between the different variables of the model and show its evolution. There are two types of variables to display:
 - Inputs: Input variables of the model. An evolution of the values taken by the variable is shown both in the historical set and in the live set.
 - Output: Variable to be predicted. For this type of variables, the comparison between the real and predicted values in the historical and live sets is shown.
- Monitoring graphic: Once you have selected a model, version and variable to be displayed, the graphic of the evaluation or comparison of predicted and actual values is shown, depending on the type of variable selected.
- Monitoring metrics for the historical set and the live data: Two tables are displayed with the numerical values of the monitoring metrics, which will depend on whether the model selected is of the classification or regression type.

The monitoring dashboard is updated twice a minute to track changes in the Cassandra database.

Figure 4: Dashboard

System was completely implemented and used a general method for the development of more than 20 research projects in the field developed by a Research Group as well as in demo projects in the R&D department of a multinational corporation proving its feasibility. The use shows as principal advantages the repeatability of the techniques, shorter learning time, better reproducibility and time saving.

4. Conclusion

The result of this work has been the implementation of a platform that allows the complete management of the life cycle associated with Machine Learning projects, taking into account the specific needs of the work environment where it has been applied. As there is no technology that covers the needs raised, the best solution is the design of a system that allows the remote development and production of data-based models based on microservices that team members can create and use according to their needs.

Due to the diverse plurality of learning models that exists today, the solution proposed in this project does not intend to be a closed prototype, but rather, it intends to propose a solution that can be extended to any project and that covers the needs of the team in charge of developing Machine Learning models.

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